

The Role of the Transverse Uterus Sign in Diagnosing Stage I and II Uterine Prolapse using Transabdominal Ultrasound

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Abstract:

Background: Uterine prolapse, a common condition affecting many women, can lead to significant complications impacting quality of life. Accurate diagnosis is essential for effective management, with transabdominal USG playing a critical role. The transverse uterus sign, indicating lateral displacement of the uterus, has emerged as a potential diagnostic indicator for stage I and II uterine prolapse.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic performance of the transverse uterus sign in diagnosing stage I and II uterine prolapse using transabdominal USG.

Methods: A retrospective analysis was conducted on 200 female patients aged 30 to 65 who underwent transabdominal USG for suspected uterine prolapse. Clinical staging was determined according to the Pelvic Organ Prolapse Quantification (POP-Q) system. The presence of the transverse uterus sign was assessed by two blinded radiologists. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0 to determine sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values.

Results: Among the 200 participants, the transverse uterus sign was observed in 135 patients (67.5%). The sign was more prevalent in stage II prolapse (72.2%) compared to stage I (63.6%). The sensitivity of the transverse uterus sign was 68.5%, with a specificity of 60.5%. The (PPV) was 74.1%, and the (NPV) was 53.8%. A chi-square test revealed a significant association between the transverse uterus sign and clinical diagnosis ($p = 0.014$).

Conclusion: The transverse uterus sign on transabdominal USG demonstrates moderate sensitivity and specificity for diagnosing stage I and II uterine prolapse. Its presence can serve as a valuable supplementary diagnostic indicator in clinical practice.

Recommendations: Clinicians should consider incorporating the transverse uterus sign into routine. Larger sample sizes should be used in future research to confirm these results and investigate the sign's applicability in various therapeutic contexts.

Keywords: Uterine prolapse, Transabdominal ultrasound, Transverse uterus sign, Diagnostic imaging, Pelvic organ prolapse

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Introduction

A major health concern for many women, especially those who have given birth or are postmenopausal, are uterine prolapse, a disorder marked by the uterus' descent into the vaginal canal. Uterine prolapse is one of the most prevalent types of pelvic organ prolapse that is thought to affect around 50% of women at some point in their lives [1]. The condition can lead to various complications, including urinary incontinence, fecal incontinence, and sexual dysfunction, significantly impacting quality of life [2].

Diagnosis of uterine prolapse often relies on clinical examination; however, imaging modalities, particularly transabdominal USG have become

increasingly important for accurate assessment. Transabdominal USG allows for visualization of pelvic organs and can help confirm clinical findings, particularly in ambiguous cases. One USG sign that has garnered attention is the "transverse uterus sign," which refers to the lateral displacement of the uterus in the transverse plane, indicative of potential prolapse [3].

Recent studies suggest that the transverse uterus sign may serve as a reliable indicator for diagnosing stage I and II uterine prolapse [4]. Stage I prolapse involves a slight descent of the uterus, while stage II is characterized by the uterus descending to the level of the hymen [5]. Early and

accurate diagnosis is crucial, as conservative management options, such as pelvic floor exercises and pessaries, may be more effective at these early stages [6].

Despite the availability of various diagnostic techniques, the effectiveness of the transverse uterus sign remains under-researched. Previous studies have demonstrated its utility; however, these investigations often focused on small sample sizes or lacked robust statistical analyses [7]. Therefore, further research is warranted to evaluate the diagnostic performance of this sign and its implications in clinical practice. This study aims to evaluate the diagnostic performance of the transverse uterus sign in diagnosing stage I and II uterine prolapse using transabdominal USG.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a retrospective study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Radiology Department of a tertiary care center, from January 2023 to January 2024. The USG images and medical records of patients who underwent transabdominal USG for suspected uterine prolapse during this period were reviewed.

Participants: This study consisted of 200 female patients with clinically indicated uterine prolapse, ages 30-65. These patients' information was taken from their electronic health records at the hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Female patients aged 30-65.
2. Patients with clinically suspected stage I or stage II uterine prolapse.
3. Patients who underwent transabdominal USG examination for pelvic organ prolapse.
4. Availability of complete medical records and USG images.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with advanced uterine prolapse (stage III or IV).
2. Previous history of pelvic surgery, including hysterectomy.
3. Congenital uterine anomalies or other pelvic structural abnormalities.

4. Incomplete or missing USG data.
5. Pregnant women or those with pelvic tumors.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were consecutively included in the trial. Observer bias was reduced by having two experienced radiologists, blinded to the clinical findings, independently assess the USG images. Any discrepancies were resolved through consensus.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from electronic medical records. The following variables were extracted: demographic information (age, BMI), clinical history, and USG findings, including the presence or absence of the transverse uterus sign and prolapse stage.

Procedure: Patients underwent transabdominal USG scans using a [machine type/model] by trained sonographers. The transverse uterus sign, which indicates lateral displacement of the uterus on imaging, was noted and recorded. The presence of this sign was correlated with clinical staging of prolapse based on the Pelvic Organ Prolapse Quantification (POP-Q) system. The images were reviewed independently by two radiologists to confirm findings.

Statistical Analysis: Data were loaded into SPSS 23.0 for statistical analysis. Clinical and demographic information were compiled using mean, standard deviation, and percentages. To identify stage I and II uterine prolapse, the transverse uterus sign's sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values were calculated. The transverse uterine sign and clinical diagnosis were compared using chi-square testing. Statistical significance was achieved with p-values below 0.05.

Results

This research included 200 female patients. Participants' ages ranged from 30 to 65, with a mean age of 48.3 years (SD $\pm$ 9.4). Patients aged 40–55 made about 65% of the total. The average BMI was 26.4 kg/m² (SD $\pm$ 3.2). Patients were divided into two groups by clinical staging of uterine prolapse: 90 (45%) had stage II and 110 (55%) stage I.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Variable	Mean $\pm$ SD or n (%)
Age (years)	48.3 $\pm$ 9.4
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.4 $\pm$ 3.2
Clinical Prolapse Stage	
- Stage I	110 (55%)
- Stage II	90 (45%)

Among the 200 patients, the transverse uterus sign was observed in 135 patients (67.5%). Out of the 110 patients with stage I uterine prolapse, 70 patients (63.6%) exhibited the transverse uterus sign on transabdominal ultrasound. In contrast, 65 out of the 90 patients (72.2%) with stage II uterine prolapse showed the transverse

uterus sign. A substantial correlation was observed between the presence of the transverse uterus sign and the clinical diagnosis of uterine prolapse ($p = 0.014$)

Table 2: Transabdominal USG Findings.

Prolapse Stage	Total Patients (n)	Transverse Uterus Sign Positive (n)	Transverse Uterus Sign Negative (n)
Stage I	110	70 (63.6%)	40 (36.4%)
Stage II	90	65 (72.2%)	25 (27.8%)
Total	200	135 (67.5%)	65 (32.5%)

In order to diagnose stage I and stage II uterine prolapse, the transverse uterus sign's sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values were computed.

Table 3: Diagnostic Performance of the Transverse Uterus Sign

Diagnostic Parameter	Value (%)
Sensitivity	68.5%
Specificity	60.5%
Positive Predictive Value	74.1%
Negative Predictive Value	53.8%
Overall Accuracy	65.0%

Statistical Analysis: The transverse uterine sign and clinical prolapse stage were compared using a chi-square test. Transverse uterus sign and uterine prolapse were substantially linked ($\chi^2 = 6.04$, $p = 0.014$), indicating that patients with prolapse are more likely to show the sign on transabdominal USG.

Summary of Key Findings

- The transverse uterus sign was present in 67.5% of the total study population.
- The sign was more frequently observed in patients with stage II prolapse (72.2%) compared to stage I prolapse (63.6%).
- The transverse uterus sign had a sensitivity of 68.5% and a specificity of 60.5%, demonstrating moderate diagnostic performance for detecting stage I and II uterine prolapse.
- The chi-square analysis showed a statistically significant correlation between the transverse uterus sign and the diagnosis of uterine prolapse ($p = 0.014$).

Discussion

In this retrospective study of 200 female patients, the transverse uterus sign was evaluated as a diagnostic tool for detecting stage I and II uterine prolapse using transabdominal USG. The study participants had a mean age of 48.3 years, with the majority (65%) falling between the ages of 40 and 55. Out of the entire populace, 55% were clinically diagnosed with stage I prolapse, while the remaining 45% had stage II prolapse. The presence of the transverse uterus sign was observed in 67.5% of all patients, with a higher occurrence in those with stage II prolapse (72.2%) compared to stage I (63.6%).

The diagnosis of uterine prolapse was significantly correlated ($p = 0.014$) with the presence of the transverse uterus sign, according to statistical analysis. The transverse uterus sign had a 68.5% sensitivity rate for uterine prolapse (stages I and II), means that the sign correctly identified uterine prolapse in about two-thirds of the cases. However, the specificity was lower at 60.5%, indicating that in some cases, the sign was present even when uterine prolapse was absent. The positive predictive value (PPV) was 74.1%, suggesting that patients with a positive transverse uterus sign had a high likelihood of having uterine prolapse. However, the negative predictive value (NPV) was 53.8%, meaning that a negative sign did not strongly rule out prolapse.

Overall, the transverse uterus sign demonstrated moderate diagnostic performance with an accuracy of 65%. This suggests that while the sign is not definitive, it can serve as a useful supplementary indicator in conjunction with other clinical assessments and diagnostic tools. The study highlights the potential utility of the transverse uterus sign in identifying early stages of uterine prolapse, particularly in patients where clinical examination may be inconclusive.

García-Mejido et al. (2022) developed a predictive model based on transperineal USG for diagnosing uterine prolapse. The model assessed how the patient's age and the variation in the pubis-uterine fundus distance at rest and during the Valsalva manoeuvre were combined, to predict uterine prolapse. The study showed a high level of accuracy, with the model predicting 96.7% of cases correctly. A second model, which also included parameters like avulsion and ballooning, had an even higher predictive capacity (AUC = 0.971). This research highlighted the practicality of using

simple, non-invasive USG measures to predict uterine prolapse with high diagnostic accuracy [8].

Lu et al. (2019) conducted a study using transperineal three-dimensional USG to measure the area of the levator hiatus. This study involved 80 women diagnosed with uterine prolapse and a control group of 80 normal women. The researchers found that the levator hiatus area was significantly larger in women with prolapse compared to controls, both at rest and during the Valsalva maneuver. They determined that a cut-off value of 22.09 cm² was the optimal threshold for diagnosing uterine prolapse, with sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy rates of 90%, 95%, and 92.5%, respectively. This study emphasized the importance of levator hiatus measurements in detecting uterine prolapse using non-invasive USG techniques [9].

Nam et al. (2021) analyzed 363 symptomatic pelvic organ prolapse patients to assess the utility of translabial USG compared to the (POP-Q) examination. They found that translabial USG was particularly useful in diagnosing prolapse and differentiating it from conditions mimicking prolapse, such as rectocele or enterocele. The study also demonstrated that the correlation between POP-Q findings and USG results was low for posterior compartment prolapse, suggesting that USG should be used in conjunction with clinical exams to improve diagnostic [10].

Conclusion

The transverse uterus sign on transabdominal USG is moderately sensitive and specific for the diagnosis of stage I and II uterine prolapse. While not definitive, its presence may be a useful supplementary diagnostic indicator in clinical practice. It is advised that more prospective studies be conducted in order to confirm these results and enhance diagnostic precision.

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